

Mechanism and evaluation of individual kinetic and thermodynamic parameters of acid bromate-lactic acid redox reaction

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Abstract : Kinetic investigations on the bromate-lactic acid redox reaction in aqueous perchloric acid medium have been carried out under varying conditions. The redox reaction exhibits first-order each in [bromate] and [lactic acid] and 1.6 order in [mineral acid]. Primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 1$) has been found to be absent. However, an inverse solvent isotope effect ($k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O} = 0.66 \pm 0.03$) is observed. Kinetic data indicate that both the species, HOBrO_2 and $\text{HOBr}^+\text{O}(\text{OH})$ of acid bromate are involving in the oxidation of lactic acid in 1 : 4 ratio, at all the studied temperatures. The mechanism proposed involves slow formation of lactic ester of bromic acid due to the nucleophilic attack by the alcoholic/hydroxyl group at the bromine atom of $\text{HOBrO}_2/\text{HOBr}^+\text{O}(\text{OH})$, which dissociates rapidly through C–C bond cleavage to form products, CH_3CHO and CO_2 . Solvent and ionic strength effects are also in accordance with the mechanism proposed. Reaction constants involved in the mechanism have been evaluated along with their thermodynamic parameters. There is a good agreement between observed and calculated rate constants under different experimental conditions.

Keywords : Lactic acid, bromate, redox reaction.

Literature survey on the oxidation of hydroxy acids shows that the oxidation proceeds either by a C–H bond cleavage to give a keto acid or by a C–C bond cleavage to give a carbonyl compound¹. Bromate, bromine(V), is known to be a powerful oxidising agent with redox potentials of 1.44 V in acid media and 0.61 V in basic media. The potentials show that Br_2 in basic solutions can disproportionate spontaneously to BrO^- and Br^- . However in acidic solutions Br_2 does not disproportionate but accumulates by an autocatalytic reaction. Therefore, in the presence of acid and an excess of bromide ions,

bromate can exclusively act as bromine generator and the resulting bromine can either brominate or oxidise the organic compound under study, depending on its constitution². Bromate oxidations of organic and inorganic reactions usually involve complications such as an

induction period, autocatalysis and involvement of two reactions³.

In view of the various mechanistic possibilities and to understand the type of cleavage and the products formed, the present study, hitherto unreported, is taken up. A detailed mechanism of acid bromate-lactic acid redox reaction is presented along with the evaluation of composite and individual kinetic and thermodynamic parameters.

Results and discussion

The reduction of bromate with excess lactic acid is autocatalytic in character. Lactic acid reacts with bromate with formation of bromine and HOBr , which are reduced further to Br^- ions. The kinetics of the reaction of lactic acid with bromine was indicated that the reactive species are Br_2 and HOBr , and that $k_{\text{HOBr}} \gg k_{\text{Br}_2}$ ⁴. Bromate ions are consumed with lactic acid and bromide ions. If bromide ions are masked in the solution by adding a suitable complexing agent such as mercury(II) ion, they cannot take part in the reactions and the over all reaction loses its autocatalytic character. This is exactly what is observed with the addition of mercury(II) acetate. Added mercuric acetate forms non-ionised mercury(II)-bromocomplexes of high stability (HgBr^+ , $K_1 = 2.5 \times 10^8$

dm³ mol⁻¹; HgBr₂, $K_2 = 3.8 \times 10^8$ dm³ mol⁻¹), without involving in the kinetic studies even with multiple concentration range of mercuric acetate⁵. In order to keep back all the Br⁻ ions formed, an optimum concentration (0.005 mol dm⁻³) of mercuric acetate is employed to pertain Br^V oxidation only.

The reaction was carried out under pseudo-first order conditions, with [lactic acid] in excess over [KBrO₃]. The effect of [bromate] on the rate of reaction was studied by varying initial [bromate] in the range 4.0–20.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³. The rate of oxidation increases with increase in [bromate]₀ and log [bromate]_t against time plots were linear ($r \geq 0.99$; $\sigma \leq 0.03$) upto three half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1 , s⁻¹) evaluated from the gradients of the plots were found to be independent of initial [bromate] (Table 1), indicating first-order dependence in [bromate]. Pseudo-first order rate constant varies linearly with increase in [lactic acid] in the range 0.01–0.10 mol dm⁻³ (Table 1). log k_1 against log [substrate] plot was linear with unit slope ($r = 0.999$; $\sigma = 0.019$). When 1/ k_1 is plotted against 1/[lactic acid] a good linear plot passing through origin was obtained, indicating no stable complex formation between the oxidant and the substrate. Further, the values of k_2 , dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ ($= k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{lactic acid}]$) were almost identical (Table 1) confirming first-order dependence in [substrate].

Table 1. Effect of varying [bromate] and [lactic acid] on the rate of reaction at 313 ± 0.1 K

[Lactic acid] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁵ k_1^a (s ⁻¹) at 10 ⁴ [bromate] (mol dm ⁻³)				
	4.0	8.0	10.0	16.0	20.0
0.01	2.73	2.70	2.71	2.72	2.71
0.02	5.42	5.40	5.43	5.41	5.46
0.04	10.82	10.87	10.86	10.84	10.83
0.08	21.76	21.69	21.70	21.72	21.68
0.10	27.14	27.26	27.10	27.32	27.19

[HClO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³; [Hg(OAc)₂] = 0.005 mol dm⁻³; HOAc-H₂O = 30–70% (v/v).

^aMean of duplicate experiments.

The effect of [HClO₄] on the rate of reaction was studied while maintaining the ionic strength constant. The reaction rate increased with increase in [HClO₄] (Table 2) and the log-log plot of k_1 against [HClO₄] was linear ($r = 0.996$; $\sigma = 0.030$) with a slope value of 1.6 ± 0.1 . A change in the concentration of added salts like NaClO₄ and Na₂SO₄ had a marginal effect (Table 3) on the rate of reaction. Changing acetic acid composition in the reaction mixture varied the dielectric constant (D) of the medium.

Table 2. Effect of varying [HClO₄] on the rate of bromate-lactic acid redox reaction at different temperatures

[HClO ₄]* (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁵ k_1^a (s ⁻¹) at				
	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K	323 K
0.05	0.38	0.57	0.78	0.98	1.59
1.00	1.41	1.88	2.70	3.43	5.49
1.50	2.74	3.93	5.57	7.12	11.40
2.00	4.63	6.64	9.40	11.88	19.16
2.50	6.79	9.38	14.01	17.89	28.70

[KBrO₃] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³; [lactic acid] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³. Other conditions as in Table 1.

*At constant ionic strength maintained by using NaClO₄.

^aMean of duplicate experiments.

Fig. 1. Verification of rate law in the form of eq. (3). Plot of $k_1/[H^+]$ against $[H^+]$ at different temperatures. Experimental conditions as in Table 2.

The rate of reaction enhanced by increasing the acetic acid content of the medium (Table 3). The inertness of the solvent towards oxidation has been tested earlier. Further, the plot of log k_1 versus 1/ D was linear with a positive slope ($r = 0.998$; $\sigma = 0.022$).

The reaction under a nitrogen atmosphere failed to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile/acrylamide monomer. Further, addition of acrylonitrile monomer to the reaction mixture had no effect on the rate of reaction, indicating non-intervention of free radicals in the reaction.

To ascertain the importance of the α -C-H bond cleavage in the rate-determining step, oxidation of DLA (α -deuteriolactic acid) was studied. The results showed that the reaction did not exhibit any primary kinetic isotope effect and $k_H/k_D = 1.0$ at all the studied temperatures.

Table 3. Dependence of rate on solvent composition and salt concentration at 313 ± 0.1 K

HOAc-H ₂ O % (v/v)	10 ⁵ k ₁ ^a (s ⁻¹)	[NaClO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁵ k ₁ ^a (s ⁻¹)	[Na ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁵ k ₁ ^a (s ⁻¹)
20-80 (59.9)*	1.36	0.5	2.71	0.50	2.71
30-70 (53.2)*	2.72	0.75	2.71	0.75	2.70
40-60 (46.5)*	5.56	1.00	2.72	1.00	2.71
50-50 (39.8)*	12.32	1.50	2.73	1.50	2.72
60-40 (33.1)*	29.90	2.00	2.72	-	-

*Dielectric constant of the medium. Other conditions as in Tables 1 and 2.

^aMean of duplicate experiments.

However, the reaction rate decreased when the reactions are carried out in D₂O and the ratio of k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O} was 0.66 ± 0.03 at all the studied temperatures. The effect of [HClO₄] on the rate of reaction was studied at different temperatures in the range 308–323 K (Table 4) to evaluate the composite (k_1 , s⁻¹) and individual rate constants (k_x and k_y) and their activation parameters. The energy of activation (E_a) corresponding to these constants was evaluated from the Arrhenius plot, from which the related thermodynamic parameters (ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger) are calculated (Table 4).

In aqueous solutions of lactic acid, 11.9% of it is present in the dissociated form when [lactic acid] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, as its K_a value is 1.38 × 10⁻⁴ at 25 °C. In 1.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid, the dissociation of lactic acid is completely suppressed and only 1.45 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³

is present in the dissociated [CH₃CH(OH)COO⁻] form, hence negligible. Therefore lactic acid is expected to be either in neutral form (S) or in its protonated form (SH⁺).

Oxidation step involves removal of H⁺ ion from the α-hydroxy functional group and the process is the driving force to the decarboxylation step. Since the protonated form would have an adverse effect on the reaction rate, the substrate should be participating in the reaction in its neutral (undissociated/unprotonated) form only. It leaves the only possibility, protonation of bromate, which could explain the enhancement in the reaction rate with acid concentration.

In moderate and strong acid solutions, bromate exists as protonated and unprotonated forms. Both HOBrO₂ and HOBr⁺O(OH) are the species of bromate existing in acid medium with protonation constants of $K_{p1} = 0.52$ and $K_{p2} = 0.21$ (dm³ mol⁻¹) at 40 °C⁴.

Therefore, in the present study it is also assumed that HOBrO₂ and HOBr⁺O(OH) are the reactive oxidant species taking part in the oxidation of lactic acid.

In spite of considerable variations in the structure, glycolic, lactic, mandelic, 2-hydroxybutyric and benzilic acids are undergoing oxidation with the same rate (2.8 ±

Table 4. Individual and composite rate constants of bromate-lactic acid redox reaction at different temperatures and activation parameters at 313 K

	Rate/formation constant at					ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (J deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K	323 K			
10 ⁵ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)	1.30 (1.36)*	1.86 (1.93)*	2.72 (2.71)*	3.76 (3.72)*	5.35 (5.39)*	53.2 ± 1.1	-163 ± 9	104.2 ± 2.6
10 ³ k _x (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	0.52	0.78	1.02	1.65	2.15	51.7 ± 0.9	-114 ± 8	87.4 ± 1.8
10 ² k _y (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	1.0	1.4	2.06	2.62	3.92	46.6 ± 0.8	-156 ± 10	95.4 ± 1.6

*Calculated rate constant using eq. (2).

[KBrO₃] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³; [lactic acid] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³; [HClO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³;

[Hg(OAc)₂] = 0.005 mol dm⁻³; HOAc-H₂O = 30-70% (v/v).

$0.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$). The structural insensitivity observed in the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by Br^{V} rules out the possibility of lactic ester of bromic acid decomposition being the rate-determining step. This step involves the cleavage of stronger C-H bond, and is bound to be influenced by structural changes in α -hydroxy acids, as is observed in chromic acid oxidation or in the oxidation with bromine⁵. The fact that benzoic acid, a hydroxy acid without an α -C-H bond, also gets oxidised under similar experimental conditions and the kinetic pattern observed is similar to that of lactic acid, confirms that the oxidation proceeds only by a C-C bond cleavage but not by a C-H bond. The absence of primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 1$) also confirms that C-H bond is not cleaved in the rate-determining step. The relative ease of oxidation of lactic acid shows that the oxidative decarboxylation is energetically more favourable and α -hydrogen is not involved in the oxidation at all. The assumption of lactic ester of bromic acid formation being the slow step could only explain the observed insensitivity to structural variations. Inorganic esterification reactions of this type are known to be not influenced by structural variations in alcohol moiety⁶.

Labile hydrogens like those present in hydroxyl/carboxyl group undergo rapid exchange in D_2O . If O-H bond is cleaved either in the rate determining step or prior to it, O-H/O-D isotope effect comes into play. This cancels the rate enhancing effect of D_2O and may result in an inverse solvent isotope effect. In the present reaction an inverse solvent isotope effect ($k_{\text{D}_2\text{O}}/k_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 0.66 \pm 0.03$) is observed, indicating that -OH group and/or -COOH group is/are involved in the rate determining step. Based on the aforesaid reasons, the possible mechanism for the oxidation of lactic acid by acid bromate is outlined in Scheme 1.

The oxidation product of C-H bond cleavage of lactic acid will be pyruvic acid ($\text{CH}_3\text{COCO}_2\text{H}$) and CH_3CHO will be the product of oxidation by C-C bond cleavage. Keeping in view the products of oxidation in the present study, being acetaldehyde and CO_2 , it is proposed the rate-determining esterification of lactic acid by Br^{V} and its rapid decomposition through C-C bond cleavage to yield acetaldehyde and CO_2 (Scheme 1).

In the above mechanistic picture (Scheme 1) formation of the lactic ester of bromic acid due to the nucleophilic attack by the alcoholic hydroxy group at the bromine atom of $\text{HOBrO}_2/\text{HOBr}^+\text{O}(\text{OH})$. However, an alternate mode of attack by the carboxyl group of lactic acid cannot be ruled out. Such an ester has been conceived in the

Scheme 1

reaction between oxalic acid and bromine, and in acid bromate oxidation of oxalic acid⁷. Kinetically these two mechanisms are not distinguishable. However, the mechanism as outlined in Scheme 1 is more probable in hydroxy acids oxidation.

HBrO_2 being a potential oxidant oxidises two more molecules of lactic acid ultimately forming Br^- ion which has been estimated using a silver nitrate solution.

The stoichiometric study also shows 1 : 3 stoichiometry between bromate and lactic acid.

The first step of which is slow and the latter fast (Scheme 1) corresponds to the rate equation :

$$-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]/dt = \{k_x + k_y K_{p_2} [\text{H}^+]\} K_{p_1} [\text{LA}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{BrO}_3^-] \quad (1)$$

which is in accord with the observed experimental facts. Ionic strength does not influence much the rate constant ($k_1, \text{ s}^{-1}$) for the reduction of bromate with lactic acid, since the slow step involves interaction of two neutral

molecules/a positive ion and dipole. The effect of dielectric constant of the medium is also in accordance with the proposed mechanism.

Dividing the rate with $[\text{BrO}_3^-]$ and rearranging eq. (1)

$$k_1 = k_x K_{p_1} [\text{LA}][\text{H}^+] + k_y K_{p_1} K_{p_2} [\text{LA}][\text{H}^+]^2 \quad (2)$$

Dividing throughout by $[\text{H}^+]$

$$\frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} = k_x K_{p_1} [\text{LA}] + k_y K_{p_1} K_{p_2} [\text{LA}][\text{H}^+] \quad (3)$$

According to eq. (3), at fixed $[\text{LA}]$, the plot of $k_1/[\text{H}^+]$ against $[\text{H}^+]$ should be linear with a definite intercept on $k_1/[\text{H}^+]$ axis, which is verified (Fig. 1, $r = 0.998$; $\sigma = 0.029$). Esterification constants (k_x and k_y) are calculated with the knowledge of K_{p_1} and K_{p_2} and from the values of intercept and slope obtained from the above plot. From the [acid] effect carried out at different temperatures (Table 2), k_x and k_y values are evaluated at each temperature (Table 4). The energy of activation corresponding to these constants (k_1 , k_x and k_y) was evaluated from the plot of $\log k$ against $1/T$, from which the related activation parameters (ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger) were calculated and recorded in Table 4. Using these k_x and k_y values, the rate constant (k_1 , s^{-1}) under different experimental conditions was calculated by eq. (2) and compared with experimental data. There is a good agreement between them (Table 4) which also supports the mechanism proposed (Scheme 1). Individual rates obtained from eq. (1) indicate that both the species viz. HOBrO_2 and $\text{HOBr}^+\text{O}(\text{OH})$ of the oxidant are involved in the oxidation of lactic acid in $\sim 1 : 4$ ratio, at all the studied temperatures (Table 4). It is pertinent to point out here that, neither HOBrO_2 alone⁷, nor $\text{HOBr}^+\text{O}(\text{OH})$ is involved/taking part in the oxidation of lactic acid by bromate in HClO_4 medium⁸.

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals used were of highest purity available. Lactic acid (Merck) was further purified by distillation under vacuum just before use. Its solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardised by cerimetry⁹. Glacial acetic acid (A.R., B.D.H.) was further purified by refluxing it with CrO_3 and acetic anhydride for 6 h and then distilled¹⁰. A stock solution of bromate was prepared by dissolving KBrO_3 (Riedel) in doubly distilled water and its concentration was determined by iodometric titration. Mercuric acetate solution was

prepared in purified acetic acid. HClO_4 (Merck) and NaClO_4 (Merck) were used to provide the required acidity and to maintain the ionic strength respectively. D_2O (purity 99.4%) was obtained from BARC, Mumbai, India. α -Deuteriolactic acid (DLA) was obtained from Merck (99.8% pure).

Product analysis : Different sets of reaction mixtures containing an excess of [lactic acid] over [bromate] in HClO_4 , and with a constant amount of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$, were kept for 12 h at 40°C in an inert atmosphere. The reaction mixture then treated with a known excess of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride solution, heated on a steam bath for 15 min and left at room temperature for an hour when the yellow crystals of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative of the product was obtained. The crystals were filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. The m.p. of the sample ($148\text{--}149^\circ\text{C}$) thus obtained coinciding well with the m.p. (148°C) of 2,4-DNP derivative of the authentic sample acetaldehyde. Therefore, acetaldehyde is the final product of oxidation under the experimental conditions. The obtained yield was $85 \pm 2\%$. CO_2 was identified by bubbling a N_2 gas through the reaction mixture and passing the liberated gas through a tube containing a saturated baryta solution. Br^- ion was estimated by adding a AgNO_3 solution, resulting in the formation of a pale yellow precipitate (AgBr). The results showed that the consumption ratio of lactic acid to bromate is 3 : 1.

Kinetic measurements : All the reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions at constant temperature, $40 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. The reaction mixture, containing lactic acid, HClO_4 and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ solutions, was thermally equilibrated and the reaction was initiated by the addition of temperature equilibrated oxidant of requisite concentration. Progress of the reaction was monitored by estimating the unreacted [bromate] to a starch end point iodometrically. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1 , s^{-1}) with respect to [bromate] were computed from the gradients of linear plots ($r \geq 0.98$; $\sigma \leq 0.03$) of $\log [\text{bromate}]_t$ against time. All most all the kinetic runs were followed to more than 80% completion of the reaction and the rate constants (k_1 , s^{-1}) were reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$.

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